

Mechanism of the Alkylation of Indoles with Nitrostyrenes Catalyzed by Chiral-at-Metal Complexes

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ABSTRACT: Chiral-at-metal rhodium(III) complexes of the formula $[\text{Rh}(\kappa^4\text{C},\text{N},\text{N}',\text{P}-\text{L})\text{A}(\text{Solv})][\text{SbF}_6]_n$ (Solv = A = MeCN, $n = 2$ (1); Solv = H₂O, A = MeCN, $n = 2$ (2); Solv = MeCN, A = Cl, $n = 1$ (3); Solv = H₂O, A = Cl, $n = 1$ (4)) catalyze the Friedel–Crafts reaction of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene and *N*-methyl-2-methylindole. Complex 4 reacts with *trans*- β -nitrostyrene, affording $[\text{RhCl}(\kappa^4\text{C},\text{N},\text{N}',\text{P}-\text{L})(\text{trans}-\beta\text{-nitrostyrene})]^+$ (5). In the presence of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole, complex 5 reversibly gives a mixture of *aci*-nitro complexes 6 in high diastereoselectivity which, in turn, evolve to the FC adducts through 1,3-prototropy mediated by a water molecule. On the basis of experimental NMR studies and DFT calculations, a detailed mechanistic pathway for the alkylation reaction is proposed, including an explanation of the origin of the measured enantiomeric ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Friedel–Crafts (FC) alkylation processes are fundamental transformations in organic syntheses that enable the formation of functionalized aromatic and heteroaromatic molecules with perfect atom economy.¹ Asymmetric versions of these transformations embody an excellent approach to obtain valuable derivatives.² In particular, asymmetric alkylation of indoles has been successfully applied in areas such as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and materials science.³ Indeed, the enantioselective Michael-type FC reaction of indoles with nitroalkenes represents an ideal strategy for the synthesis of biologically active indole-based compounds such as β -carbolines, α -substituted tryptamines, or tryptophan analogues.⁴ In the last few years, both organo-^{3,5} and metal-catalyzed^{3,5a} FC alkylations of indoles with nitroalkenes have been reported. Among the latter, homogeneous metallic systems based on copper or zinc and, to a lesser extent, nickel, platinum, or palladium were successfully applied. However, although reasonable reaction models, mostly based on the catalytic outcome, were proposed, scarce experimental and/or theoretical studies about the catalytic transformation have been reported so far.

In the context of the present work, reactions mediated by asymmetric catalysts stereogenic only at metal have gained a special interest.⁶ In particular, Meggers' group has reported that chiral-at-metal biscyclometalated iridium(III) complexes catalyze the enantioselective FC alkylation of indoles with α,β -unsaturated 2-acylimidazoles⁷ acting as Lewis acids. In addition, the same group has shown that related saturated (18 e⁻) iridium complexes of this class are active catalysts for the enantioselective FC alkylation of indoles with α -

substituted⁸ or β,β -disubstituted⁹ nitroalkenes through a number of hydrogen bond interactions with the ligand sphere of the bis-cyclometalated iridium complexes. In both cases, excellent yields and enantioselectivities were achieved.

We have recently reported the preparation of a family of chiral-at-metal rhodium(III) complexes of formula $[\text{Rh}(\kappa^4\text{C},\text{N},\text{N}',\text{P}-\text{L})\text{A}(\text{Solv})][\text{SbF}_6]_n$ containing the tetradentate tripodal ligand L (Scheme 1).¹⁰ Remarkably, only the

Scheme 1. Octahedral Complexes with the Tripodal Tetradentate Ligand L

diastereomer in which the phosphorus and pyridinic nitrogen atoms are mutually *trans* was detected and isolated in high yield. Moreover, the sign of the chirality adopted by the metal predetermines the configuration at the aminic nitrogen and, therefore, the complexes were obtained as a racemic mixture of a pair of enantiomers. Very recently, we have reported the resolution of these racemates by using (*S*)- or (*R*)-phenylglycine as the chiral auxiliary.¹¹

It is interesting to note that the tripodal tetradentate mode of coordination of the ligand L maintains the configuration at

the metal even under harsh conditions, whereas the two remaining coordination sites are available for catalytic transformations.^{10,11} Hence, these types of complexes are well suited for stereochemical studies.

In this paper, we report on the application of these chiral-metal rhodium(III) complexes in the alkylation of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole with *trans*- β -nitrostyrene and, on the basis of experimental NMR studies and DFT calculations, we present a detailed mechanistic proposal for this catalytic process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Complexes 1–4¹² catalyze the FC alkylation of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole with *trans*- β -nitrostyrene. Table 1 gives a selection of the results together with the reaction conditions employed. On the whole, moderate to good conversions were achieved with low enantiomeric ratio (*er*) values.

Table 1. Friedel–Crafts Reactions Catalyzed by 1–4, at 298 K^a

entry ^a	cat.	cat. loading (%)	<i>t</i> (h)	conversn (%) ^b	<i>er</i> ^c
1	(C)-1	10	1	90	59/41 <i>S/R</i>
2	(C)-1	10	17	98	59/41 <i>S/R</i>
3	<i>rac</i> -2	5	5	93	
4	(A)-2	10	0.75	81	62/38 <i>S/R</i>
5	(A)-2	10	17	98	62/38 <i>S/R</i>
6	(A)-3	10	0.83	30	53/47 <i>S/R</i>
7	(A)-3	10	17	40	53/47 <i>S/R</i>
8	<i>rac</i> -4	5	18	42	
9	(A)-4	5	22	40	55/45 <i>S/R</i>
10	(A)-4	10	1.25	32	50/50
11	(A)-4	10	17	54	50/50

^aReaction conditions: catalyst, 1.16×10^{-3} or 2.32×10^{-3} mmol (5 or 10 mol %); *trans*- β -nitrostyrene, 3.48×10^{-2} mmol; *N*-methyl-2-methylindole, 2.32×10^{-2} mmol; 10 mg of 4 Å molecular sieves in 0.5 mL of CD₂Cl₂. ^bBased on indole. Determined by ¹H NMR. ^cDetermined by HPLC.

To obtain information about the steps of the process, the reaction of complex 4 with *trans*- β -nitrostyrene was monitored by NMR spectroscopy. When, at 298 K, 1 equiv of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene was added to a solution of 4 in CD₂Cl₂, in the presence of 4 Å molecular sieves, the new complex [RhCl(κ^4 C₂N,N',P-L)(*trans*- β -nitrostyrene)]⁺ (5) formed (eq 1). In

the presence of 4 Å molecular sieves the equilibrium between complexes 4 and 5 is shifted to the right (Supporting Information). The presence of two doublets centered at 7.68 and 7.48 ppm in the ¹H NMR spectrum, attributed to the H_α and H_β protons, respectively, denotes the coordinated nitroalkene. Correspondingly, two peaks at 140.99 (C_β) and 131.87 (C_α) ppm are detected in the ¹³C NMR spectrum.

The observed sharp set of NMR signals, from 298 to 193 K, indicates that only one species is present in solution. Nevertheless, as a result of the rotation at the Rh–O bond

and/or the *s-cis/s-trans* conformation of the C–N bond, DFT calculations reveal that the structures I–VI are possible for (A)-5¹² (Figure 1). Notably, in each complex short intramolecular

Figure 1. View of the calculated structures I–VI of (A)-[RhCl(κ^4 C₂N,N',P-L)(*trans*- β -nitrostyrene)]⁺ (5) with relative Gibbs free energies (298 K, CH₂Cl₂, kcal mol⁻¹). For clarity the clear enantioface (*Re*, *Si*) of coordinated *trans*- β -nitrostyrene is indicated for each isomer and most hydrogen atoms are omitted.

contacts (CH \cdots O, CH \cdots π , or CH \cdots Cl) anchor the coordinated *trans*- β -nitrostyrene to the chiral pocket (see the Supporting Information) and only one enantioface (*Re* or *Si*, Figure 1) of this ligand is clear and, therefore, is expected to be more reactive. In view of the relative stabilities of I–VI and the NMR data, I should be the only species observed in solution in the explored range of temperature.

Once it is formed in situ from *rac*-4 and *trans*- β -nitrostyrene, 5 reacts, at 273 K, with *N*-methyl-2-methylindole (1/1 molar ratio, see the Supporting Information), affording five diastereomers of the rhodium *aci*-nitro complex 6 (eq 2) in

a molar ratio of ca. 93:4:1:1:1. Complexes 6 were isolated as a mixture of these diastereomers, and the major isomer was spectroscopically characterized. The most characteristic ¹H NMR signal is a NO₂H singlet at 11.27 ppm. The H_α proton

exhibits NOE relationships with the 6-CH(Py) (see eq 2) and OH protons and the H_β proton with the 2-methylindole protons.

Notably, at 248 K, ¹H-¹H EXSY cross peaks between the H_β and NMe protons of the major (93%) and the second more abundant (4%) isomers of **6** (Supporting Information) indicate that these two isomers exchange with each other. Moreover, we did not observe exchange between free *N*-methyl-2-methylindole and the *aci*-nitro fragment in **6**. Therefore, the retro-FC reaction, although viable (vide infra), cannot be responsible for the observed exchange process. These data indicate that at least 97% of the stereogenic carbon formed in **6** (CH_β) has to have the same configuration.

The formation of the mixture of *aci*-nitro derivatives **6** was elucidated by means of DFT calculations. For all of the *trans*-β-nitrostyrene complexes **X** (X = I–VI), the *aci*-nitro derivatives B^{X_{Re/Si}} form as a result of the following steps: (i) formation of the chiral intermediate A^{X_{Re/Si}} by means of the nucleophilic attack of the incoming *N*-methyl-2-methylindole to the β-carbon of the coordinated *trans*-β-nitrostyrene; (ii) 1,5-prototropy rendering B^{X_{Re/Si}} (Scheme 2).¹³

Scheme 2. (Top) Reaction Sequence for the Formation of *aci*-Nitro Derivatives B^{X_{Re/Si}} and (Bottom) Stable *aci*-Nitro Derivatives Obtained from II–V along with the Calculated Percentages^b

^aX = I–VI (cf. Figure 1). For brevity only the nucleophilic attack through the *Re* enantioface of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole is shown.

^bThe *Re/Si* descriptor in the superscript indicates the enantioface of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole implied in the nucleophilic attack to carbon-β of coordinated *trans*-β-nitrostyrene.

The stereochemical configuration of the *aci*-nitro derivatives is straightforwardly determined from the reactive enantioface of *trans*-β-nitrostyrene: namely, the diastereomer with *S* (*R*) configuration at the new carbon stereocenter is obtained by the attack to the coordinated *trans*-β-nitrostyrene through its *Re* (*Si*) enantioface. The Gibbs energy profiles for I–VI (see the Supporting Information) indicate that the formation of *aci*-nitro derivatives B^{X_{Re/Si}} should be reversible. In addition, except for III, the nucleophilic attack of the indole to the coordinated nitrostyrene should be slower than the following 1,5-prototropy. Also, considering (A)-4 as the starting metal complex and assuming that an equilibrium mixture of *aci*-nitro derivatives is finally achieved, five *aci*-nitro derivatives should

be observed: namely, (S)-B^{IV_{Re}} (72%), (S)-B^{V_{Re}} (16%), (S)-B^{II_{Re}} (5%), (R)-B^{III_{Si}} (5%), and (S)-B^{V_{Si}} (2%) (*S/R* ratio 95/5, Scheme 2).

Notably, these data broadly suit the composition, measured by ¹H NMR, of the mixture resulting from the stoichiometric reaction (vide supra). Furthermore, the calculated structures of (S)-B^{IV_{Re}} and (S)-B^{V_{Re}} (Figure 2) nicely fit in with the

Figure 2. Views of the calculated structures of (S)-B^{IV_{Re}} and (S)-B^{V_{Re}}. Selected angles (deg) and interatomic distances (Å) are Rh–O–N–C –11.0 (B^{IV_{Re}}), 75.8 (B^{V_{Re}}), H_α...6-CH(Py) 2.7 (B^{IV_{Re}}), and H_β...H^{2-Me} 3.1 (average, B^{IV_{Re}}). Most hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

observed NOESY and EXSY patterns. Indeed, in agreement with the NOESY cross peaks between H_α and the 6-CH(Py) hydrogen observed for the major *aci*-nitro derivative **6** (vide supra), an H...H interatomic distance of 2.7 Å between H_α and the 6-CH(Py) hydrogen has been observed for the most stable *aci*-nitro isomer B^{IV_{Re}} (Figure 2). Further, it is worth mentioning that interatomic distances >4.0 Å between H_α and the 6-CH(Py) hydrogen atom were observed in the structure of the remaining *aci*-nitro derivatives B^X. Also, in accordance with the NOE correlation between H_β and the 2-methyl at the indolyl moiety for the major diastereomer **6**, the average H...H interatomic distance between these hydrogen atoms in B^{IV_{Re}} is 3.1 Å. Finally, confirming the exchange cross-peaks between the observed major *aci*-nitro isomers (vide supra; see the Supporting Information), an inspection of the calculated structures B^{IV_{Re}} and B^{V_{Re}} reveals that their interconversion can be easily accomplished by rotating the dihedral angle Rh–O–N–C by ca. 90° (Figure 2).

When solutions of the *aci*-nitro complexes **6** were heated to 298 K, the slow and gradual formation of the FC adduct was observed (eq 3). In this regard, we have recently shown that, in

half-sandwich rhodium complexes, the formation of the FC adduct from *aci*-nitro complexes involves two competitive steps: i.e., dissociation of the coordinated *aci*-nitro and a 1,3-prototropic tautomerism. Indeed, the two possible intermedi-

ates, free *aci*-nitro and catalyst–FC adduct compounds, were detected.¹⁴ However, in the course of the evolution of complexes **6** to the FC adducts, no intermediates were detected, even at 248 K, and the relative concentration of the *aci*-nitro complexes remains essentially constant.

As stated above, experimental data and DFT calculations indicate that starting from (*A*)-**4** the configuration of the new chiral carbon center for the two major *aci*-nitro complexes **6**, which account for about 97% of the rhodium derivatives present in the reaction medium, is *S*. However, in the catalytic outcome *S*/*R* enantiomeric ratios of only 55/45 or even poorer were obtained (entries 9–11, Table 1). As the new stereogenic carbon center is already generated in **6**, the lower obtained could be explained by assuming that the formation of **6** is reversible. Indeed, on the addition of *trans*-4-chloro- β -nitrostyrene to *N*-methyl-2-methylindole, free *aci*-nitro complexes **6** afforded the corresponding *aci*-nitro complexes **6'**, derived from the chlorinated nitroalkene (eq 4).

Figure 3 shows the ¹H (low-field region) and the ³¹P{¹H} NMR spectra of a mixture of complexes **6** (Figure 3A) and the

Figure 3. Selected regions of ¹H and ³¹P{¹H} NMR spectra at 248 K before (A) and after (B) the addition of *trans*-4-chloro- β -nitrostyrene to a mixture of complexes **6**.

same spectra upon the addition of 2 equiv of the chlorinated nitrostyrene (Figure 3B). The apparent formation of **6'**, from **6** and the chlorinated nitrostyrene, demonstrates that the attack of the indole to the coordinated nitrostyrene to render *aci*-nitros **6** is reversible to some extent. As expected, the evolution of mixtures of *aci*-nitros **6** and **6'** gives rise to a mixture of the two FC adducts derived from *N*-methyl-2-methylindole and each of the two involved nitrostyrenes.

The reversibility of the reaction of formation of *aci*-nitros **6** (eq 2) explains that the enantioselectivity of the catalytic reaction does not coincide with the diastereoselectivity measured in the formation of the *aci*-nitro complexes. However, it does not justify the low value of enantioselectivity encountered. To explain this fact, as well as to shed light on relevant intermediates and transition states, the FC reaction from *trans*- β -nitrostyrene complexes I–VI was explored by means of DFT calculations (see the Supporting Information). As a general pattern, the FC product (**C^X**) is the result of the 1,3-prototropy within an H–O–N=C moiety. Nevertheless, the direct 1,3-prototropy in the *aci*-nitro derivatives **B^X** (**X** = I–VI) is not kinetically affordable ($\Delta G_{\text{act}} > 40 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and the assistance of a proton shuttle has to be invoked. As a matter of fact, similarly to related processes,¹⁵ affordable barriers have been calculated for the water-assisted prototropy in the *aci*-nitro derivatives **B^{IV}_{Re/Si}** (*Re*, 21.8 kcal mol⁻¹; *Si*, 18.0 kcal mol⁻¹) and **B^V_{Re/Si}** (*Re*, 16.2 kcal mol⁻¹ (Figure 4, top); *Si*, 20.8 kcal mol⁻¹). On the other hand, the steric hindrance at the H–O–N=C moiety of the *aci*-nitro derivatives **B^X_{Re/Si}** (**X** = I–III, VI) prevents the approach of one water molecule to this moiety. Thus, the early isomerization of these *aci*-nitro derivatives via a concerted transition state should take place (16.3–28.1 kcal mol⁻¹; as an example

Figure 4. Overall Gibbs free energy profiles (298 K, CH₂Cl₂, kcal mol⁻¹) for the FC reaction from **V** (top) and **VI** (bottom) and reaction sequences from the *aci*-nitro intermediates (*S*)-**B^V_{Re}** and (*R*)-**B^{VI}_{Re}** (cf. Scheme 2).

see Figure 4, bottom, for TS_{B^{VI}-B_i^{VI}}), rendering an accessible H–O–N=C moiety prone to undergo the water-assisted 1,3-prototropy (9.8–28.3 kcal mol⁻¹, Supporting Information).

The pathways from I–VI were compared on the basis of the energetic span model.¹⁶ The calculated energetic spans (δE) along with the TOF-determining intermediate (TDI) and the TOF-determining transition state (TDTS) are given in the Supporting Information. Notably, when I–VI are compared, the Gibbs free energy profiles of V and VI for the nucleophilic attack from the *Re* enantioface of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole feature the lowest δE (V, 16.2 kcal mol⁻¹; VI, 16.3 kcal mol⁻¹, Figure 4). Consequently V and VI should be the most reactive and should provide the highest TOFs. For the sake of comparison, the catalytic cycle starting from IV exhibits the next higher energetic span ($\delta E = 18.0$ kcal mol⁻¹) and consequently should provide significantly lower productivity (TOF _{$\delta E=18.0$} /TOF _{$\delta E=16.2$} $\approx 5 \times 10^{-4}$), making unimportant the contribution of IV to the formation of the FC product.¹⁷

Regarding the expected enantioselectivity when (A)-4 is the catalytic precursor, the clear (reactive) enantiofaces of nitrostyrene in V and VI are opposite, namely *Re* and *Si*, respectively, V rendering the *S* enantiomer and VI the *R* enantiomer of the FC product (Figure 4). Thus, in view of the similar energetic spans of the pathways from V and from VI, an almost racemic mixture of FC enantiomers should form, which nicely suits the poor er observed in the catalytic tests (Table 1).

On the basis of the sequential steps discussed above, the catalytic cycle depicted in Figure 5 can be proposed. The

Figure 5. Proposed catalytic cycle for the FC reaction between *trans*- β -nitrostyrene and *N*-methyl-2-methylindole; [Rh] = {RhCl(κ^4 C,N,N',P-L)}.

coordinated water molecule in 4 is displaced by *trans*- β -nitrostyrene to give the nitroalkene complex 5. The reversible attack of the indole at the activated C $_{\beta}$ of the coordinated nitroalkene diastereoselectively renders the *aci*-nitro complexes 6. Complexes 6 rearrange to the undetected catalyst–adduct complex through a 1,3-prototropic tautomerism. A further molecule of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene replaces the FC adduct and regenerates complex 5, which restarts the cycle.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, a plausible mechanism for the enantioselective alkylation of indole with nitrostyrenes mediated by chiral-metal catalysts has been proposed. In particular, for complex 4, the formation of the new stereocenter from indole attack on the coordinated nitrostyrene takes place with high diastereoselectivity ($\geq 97/3$, step 5 \rightarrow 6). This feature strongly indicates that the chiral pocket created around the metal by the ligand L in complexes with octahedral geometry^{10,11} is well suited for asymmetric induction. However, the stereochemical outcome of the reaction under study is not determined by the step in which the stereogenic center is formed but instead is correlated with the relative reactivity of the diastereomeric *aci*-nitro intermediates downstream in the catalytic cycle. Nonetheless, when we take into account the remarkable high stereoselection observed in the formation of the carbon stereocenter, the easy tuning of the steric and electronic properties of the modular ligand L, and the possibility of preparing octahedral complexes of metals different from rhodium, the results reported herein open the door to the efficient application of enantiopure compounds related to 1–4 in a broad variety of asymmetric transformations.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General Information. All manipulations were performed under an inert atmosphere of argon by using Schlenk or NMR tube techniques. Dry, oxygen-free solvents were employed. ¹H, ¹³C, and ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded on ARX 300, AV 400, and AV 500 (Bruker) spectrometers. ¹H and ¹³C NMR chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to SiMe₄ as standard. ³¹P NMR downfield chemical shifts are expressed in ppm relative to 85% H₃PO₄. ¹H correlation spectra were obtained using standard procedures. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FT IR spectrophotometer. Carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen analyses were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240 B microanalyzer. Analytical high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was performed on an Alliance Waters (Water 2996 PDA detector) instrument using chiral column Chiralpak IB (0.46 cm \times 25 cm).

Catalytic Procedure. At room temperature, in an NMR tube, to a solution of 1–4 (1.16 $\times 10^{-3}$ or 2.32 $\times 10^{-3}$ mmol (5 or 10 mol %)) and 5.18 mg (3.48 $\times 10^{-2}$ mmol) of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene in CD₂Cl₂ (0.3 mL) was added about 10 mg of 4 Å MS. After 20 min at 298 K, a solution of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole (2.32 $\times 10^{-2}$ mmol) in CD₂Cl₂ (0.2 mL) was added. The resulting mixture was analyzed by ¹H NMR. After the appropriate reaction time, the reaction was quenched by addition of a methanolic solution of [N(*n*Bu)₄]Br, and the catalytic residue was analyzed by HPLC.

Preparation and Characterization of the Nitro Complex 5.

In an NMR tube, at 298 K, to a solution of 15.0 mg (0.017 mmol) of RhCl(κ^4 C,N,N',P-L)(OH₂)[SbF₆]₂ (*rac*-4) and 2.85 mg (0.019 mmol) of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene in CD₂Cl₂ (0.5 mL) was added 4 Å MS (ca. 10 mg). The resulting solution was analyzed by NMR spectroscopy without any further purification and showed the presence of complex 5.

¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 9.02 (br s, 1H, 6-CH(Py)), 7.92 (pt, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 7.71 (m, 4H, H(Ar)), 7.68 (d, *J* = 13.5 Hz, 1H, H $_{\alpha}$), 7.66 (m, 1H, H(Ar)), 7.56–7.40 (m, 13H, H(Ar)), 7.48 (d, *J* = 13.5 Hz, 1H, H $_{\beta}$), 7.18 (br, 2H, H(Ar)),

7.12 (pt, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 7.07 (d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 1H, 6-CH(Ph)), 6.75 (pt, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1H, 4-CH(Ph)), 6.65 (pt, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H, 5-CH(Ph)), 6.41 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 1H, 3-CH(Ph)), 4.88 (d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Py)), 4.75 (d, $J = 13.4$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(P)), 4.62 (d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Py)), 4.49 (d, $J = 17.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Ph)), 4.47 (brd, $J = 13.4$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(P)), and 3.87 (d, $J = 17.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Ph)). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125.77 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 156.58 (s, 2-C(Py)), 149.27 (s, 6-CH(Py)), 146.78 (s, 2-C(Ph)), 144.78 (dd, $J_{Rh-C} = 32.4$ Hz, $J_{P-C} = 9.6$ Hz, CRh), 140.99 (s, C _{β}), 140.38 (s, CH(Ar)), 139.72 (d, $J = 17.2$ Hz, 2-C(PhP)), 136.97 (s, CH(Ar)), 136.70 (s, 6-CH(Ph)), 135.75 (s, CH(Ar)), 134.53 (m, 5C, CH(Ar)), 133.54 (s, CH(Ar)), 133.05 (s, CH(Ar)), 131.87 (s, C _{α}), 131.38 (s, CH(Ar)), 130.59 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, CH(Ar)), 129.88 (s, 2C, CH(Ar)), 129.84 (s, C(Ar)), 129.68 (s, 2C, CH(Ar)), 129.42 (d, $J = 10.0$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.72 (d, $J = 10.9$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.37 (s, 5-CH(Ph)), 126.35 (d, $J = 47.8$ Hz, C(Ar)), 125.89 (br s, CH(Ar)), 125.00 (d, $J = 61.8$ Hz, C(Ar)), 124.50 (s, 4-CH(Ph)), 123.84 (d, $J = 52.0$ Hz, C(Ar)), 122.92 (s, CH(Ar)), 120.42 (s, 3-CH(Ph)), 72.18 (s, CH₂(Py)), 67.27 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, CH₂(P)), and 64.51 (s, CH₂(Ph)). ³¹P{¹H} NMR (202.46 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 30.53 (d, $J = 128.2$ Hz).

Preparation and Characterization of the *aci*-Nitro Complexes 6.

At room temperature, to a solution of 100.0 mg (0.116 mmol) of [RhCl(κ^4 C₄N₄N',P-L)(OH₂)] [SbF₆] (*rac-4*) in 20 mL of CH₂Cl₂ were added 19.0 mg (0.127 mmol) of *trans*- β -nitrostyrene and 100 mg of 4 Å MS. After 20 min of vigorous stirring, the solution was cooled to 273 K and 18.5 mg (0.127 mmol) of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole was added. The solution changed from dark red to light yellow. After 1 h at room temperature, the 4 Å MS was filtered off and the resulting solution was concentrated under vacuum until ca. 3 mL. After the addition of 15 mL of Et₂O and 5 mL of *n*-pentane, the precipitation of a pale solid was observed, which was washed with *n*-pentane (3 \times 3 mL) and vacuum-dried. Yield: 85.8 mg (65%). Anal. Calcd for C₅₀H₄₆ClF₆N₄O₂PRhSb·2H₂O: C, 51.07; H, 4.29; N, 4.76. Found: C, 50.75; H, 4.46; N, 4.36. IR (solid, cm⁻¹): ν (OH) 3600 (vbr), ν (NOH) 2944 (br), ν (C=N) 1608 (s), ν (SbF₆) 651 (s). The isolated solid is a mixture of five isomers in a ca. 93/4/1/1/1 molar ratio.

Isomer 6a (93%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.27 (s, 1H, OH), 8.62 (pt, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 1H, 6-CH(Py)), 7.77 (ptd, $J = 7.5$, 1.6 Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 7.74–7.35 (m, 14H, H(Ar)), 7.32–7.16 (m, 5H, H(Ar)), 7.03 (pt, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 6.98 (brd, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H, H(Ar)), 6.89 (m, 3H, 6-CH(Ph), 2 \times H(Ar)), 6.87 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H, H _{α}), 6.78 (pt, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 6.67 (m, 2H, 4-CH(Ph), 5-CH(Ph)), 6.29 (d, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H, 3-CH(Ph)), 4.16 (d, $J = 17.6$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Ph)), 3.80 (s, 3H, NMe), 3.68 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H, H _{β}), 3.60 (d, $J = 13.6$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(P)), 3.52 (d, $J = 17.7$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Ph)), 3.33 (d, $J = 15.3$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Py)), 3.11 (brd, $J = 13.2$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(P)), 2.68 (d, $J = 15.4$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Py)), and 1.85 (s, 3H, Me). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125.77 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 156.64 (s, 2-C(Py)), 148.10 (s, 6-CH(Py)), 147.68 (s, 2-C(Ph)), 145.22 (dd, $J_{Rh-C} = 30.8$ Hz, $J_{P-C} = 9.9$ Hz, CRh), 139.88 (s, CH(Ar)), 139.66 (d, $J = 16.4$ Hz, 2-C(PhP)), 139.65 (s, C(Ar)), 136.59 (s, C(Ar)), 135.45 (s, CH(Ar)), 135.09 (s, CH(Ar)), 134.27 (d, $J = 9.4$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 134.17 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, CH(Ar)), 133.96 (s, C(Ar)), 133.56 (s, CH(Ar)), 132.54 (s, CH(Ar)), 131.75 (br s, CH(Ar)), 131.50 (br s, CH(Ar)), 130.40 (d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH(Ar)), 129.57 (brd, $J = 5.7$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 129.23 (s, 2C, CH(Ar)), 129.03 (d, $J = 10.3$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.60 (d, $J = 12.5$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.55 (s, 2C, CH(Ar)),

127.05 (d, $J = 48.2$ Hz, C(Ar)), 127.03 (s, C _{α}), 126.69 (s, 4-CH(Ph)), 125.98 (s, C(Ar)), 125.36 (br s, CH(Ar)), 124.25 (d, $J = 60.4$ Hz, C(Ar)), 124.13 (s, CH(Ar)), 123.32 (d, $J = 52.6$ Hz, C(Ar)), 122.06 (br s, CH(Ar)), 121.75 (s, CH(Ar)), 120.25 (s, 6-CH(Ph)), 119.95 (s, 3-CH(Ph)), 117.52 (s, 5-CH(Ph)), 110.54 (s, CH(Ar)), 107.76 (s, C(Ar)), 70.83 (s, CH₂(Py)), 64.95 (s, CH₂(Ph)), 64.50 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, CH₂(P)), 39.97 (s, C _{β}), 30.03 (s, NMe), and 10.95 (s, Me). ³¹P{¹H} NMR (202.46 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 32.60 (d, $J = 127.8$ Hz).

Isomer 6b (4%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.65 (s, 1H, OH), 8.79 (br s, 1H, 6-CH(Py)), 7.11 (overlapped, 1H, H _{α}), 4.07 (br s, 1H, H _{β}), and 3.53 (s, 3H, NMe). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125.77 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 125.66 (s, C _{α}), 40.63 (s, C _{β}), and 29.90 (s, NMe). ³¹P{¹H} NMR (202.46 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 31.63 (d, $J = 127.6$ Hz).

Isomer 6c (1%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.51 (s, 1H, OH).

Isomer 6d (1%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.47 (s, 1H, OH).

Isomer 6e (1%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.32 (s, 1H, OH).

Preparation and Characterization of the *aci*-Nitro Complexes 6'.

In an NMR tube, at room temperature, to a solution of 25.0 mg (0.029 mmol) of RhCl(κ^4 C₄N₄N',P-L)(OH₂) [SbF₆] (*rac-4*) and 7.97 mg (0.043 mmol) of *trans*-4-chloro- β -nitrostyrene in CD₂Cl₂ (0.5 mL) was added 4 Å MS (ca. 10 mg). After 20 min, the solution was cooled to 273 K and 4.20 mg (0.029 mmol) of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole was added. After 30 min of reaction at 298 K, the solution was analyzed by NMR spectroscopy, at 248 K, without any further purification and showed the presence of complexes 6' in a ca. 90/6/2/1/1 molar ratio.

Isomer 6'a (90%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.36 (s, 1H, OH), 8.62 (br pt, $J = 4.2$ Hz, 1H, 6-CH(Py)), 7.75 (m, 1H, H(Ar)), 7.72–7.37 (m, 14H, H(Ar)), 7.32–7.21 (m, 5H, H(Ar)), 7.03 (ddd, $J = 9.0$, 7.8, 0.9 Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 6.94–6.88 (m, 3H, 6-CH(Ph), 2 \times H(Ar)), 6.85 (brd, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 6.83 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H, H _{α}), 6.79 (ptd, $J = 7.6$, 0.8 Hz, 1H, H(Ar)), 6.67 (m, 2H, 4-CH(Ph), 5-CH(Ph)), 6.30 (dd, $J = 7.1$, 2.0 Hz, 1H, 3-CH(Ph)), 4.17 (d, $J = 17.6$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Ph)), 3.82 (s, 3H, NMe), 3.65 (d, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1H, H _{β}), 3.59 (d, $J = 13.3$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(P)), 3.53 (d, $J = 17.6$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Ph)), 3.35 (d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-S*-CH₂(Py)), 3.14 (brd, $J = 13.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(P)), 2.67 (d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, 1H, *pro-R*-CH₂(Py)), and 1.84 (s, 3H, Me). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125.77 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 156.63 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 2-C(Py)), 148.11 (s, 6-CH(Py)), 147.69 (s, 2-C(Ph)), 145.20 (dd, $J_{Rh-C} = 31.6$ Hz, $J_{P-C} = 10.0$ Hz, CRh), 139.91 (s, CH(Ar)), 139.65 (d, $J = 17.0$ Hz, 2-C(PhP)), 138.17 (s, C(Ar)), 137.57 (s, CH(Ar)), 136.62 (s, C(Ar)), 135.45 (s, CH(Ar)), 135.10 (br s, CH(Ar)), 134.13 (s, C(Ar)), 133.20 (s, C(Ar)), 134.30 (d, $J = 9.1$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 134.19 (d, $J = 9.5$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 133.60 (br s, CH(Ar)), 131.65 (br s, CH(Ar)), 131.54 (br s, CH(Ar)), 130.79 (s, CH(Ar)), 130.43 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, CH(Ar)), 129.86 (s, CH(Ar)), 129.22 (s, CH(Ar)), 129.08 (s, CH(Ar)), 128.98 (s, CH(Ar)), 128.87 (d, $J = 3.3$ Hz, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.81 (br, 2C, CH(Ar)), 127.15 (d, $J = 48.9$ Hz, C(Ar)), 126.71 (s, 5-CH(Ph)), 126.45 (s, C _{α}), 125.90 (s, C(Ar)), 125.37 (d, $J = 3.1$ Hz, CH(Ar)), 124.43 (d, $J = 60.6$ Hz, C(Ar)), 124.16 (s, 4-CH(Ph)), 123.28 (d, $J = 53.2$ Hz, C(Ar)), 122.08 (d, $J = 1.6$ Hz, 6-CH(Ph)), 121.86 (s, CH(Ar)), 120.35 (s, CH(Ar)), 119.97 (s, 3-CH(Ph)), 117.38 (br s, CH(Ar)), 110.65 (s, CH(Ar)), 107.19 (s, C(Ar)), 70.80 (s, CH₂(Py)), 64.91 (s,

CH₂(Ph)), 64.64 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, CH₂(P)), 39.33 (s, C_β), 30.05 (s, NMe), and 10.91 (s, Me). ³¹P{¹H} NMR (202.46 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 32.56 (d, *J* = 128.0 Hz).

Isomer 6'b (6%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.74 (s, 1H, OH), 8.59 (br s, 1H, 6-CH(Py)), 7.00 (br s, 1H, H_α), and 4.21 (overlapped, 1H, H_β). ¹³C{¹H} NMR (125.77 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 125.31 (s, C_α), 40.40 (s, C_β). ³¹P{¹H} NMR (202.46 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 31.50 (d, *J* = 132.7 Hz).

Isomer 6'c (2%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.54 (s, 1H, OH).

Isomer 6'd (1%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.46 (s, 1H, OH).

Isomer 6'e (1%). ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CD₂Cl₂, 248 K, ppm): δ 11.32 (s, 1H, OH).

Study of the Reversible Formation of the *aci*-Nitro Complexes 6 and 6'. In an NMR tube, at 273 K, to a solution of 25.0 mg (0.029 mmol) of [RhCl(κ⁴C,N,N',P-L)(OH₂)] [SbF₆]₂ (*rac*-4) and *trans*-β-nitrostyrene (6.48 mg, 0.043 mmol) in CD₂Cl₂ (0.3 mL) was added 4 Å MS (ca. 10 mg). After 30 min, a solution of *N*-methyl-2-methylindole (4.20 mg, 0.029 mmol) in CD₂Cl₂ (0.2 mL) was added. After 30 min at room temperature, the *N*-methyl-2-methylindole was not detectable by ¹H NMR. Then, at 273 K, 10.63 mg (0.058 mmol) of *trans*-4-chloro-β-nitrostyrene was added. After 15 min at 248 K, the NMR spectra of ¹H and ³¹P{¹H} showed almost an equimolar mixture of *aci*-nitro complexes 6 and 6'.

DFT Calculations. Molecular structure optimizations and frequency calculations were carried out with the Gaussian09 program (revision D.01)¹⁸ using the method B3PW91,¹⁹ including the D3 dispersion correction scheme by Grimme with Becke–Johnson damping.²⁰ The def2-SVP²¹ basis and pseudopotential were used for all atoms, and the “ultrafine” grid was employed in all calculations. Stationary points were characterized by vibrational analysis. All of the structures were optimized in CH₂Cl₂ (298 K) using the PCM method.²² Atomic coordinates of calculated structures are given in *coordinates_DFT.pdf*.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: 10.1021/acs.organo- met.8b00925.

Further details of experimental methods and DFT calculations (PDF)

Cartesian coordinates of the calculated structures (XYZ)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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(13) The steric congestion at the metal center hampers the rotation around the newly formed C–C bond, thus preventing the fast interconversion of rotamers B^{X-Re} and B^{X-Si} ($X = I-VI$) obtained as a consequence of the different reactive enantiofaces of the *N*-methyl-2-methylindole.

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